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SYNTHESIS AND CHEMICAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF METHYL ESTER OF ADAMANTAN-1-THIONACETIC ACID IN REACTION WITH PIPERIDINE

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Abstract

When adamantane-1-acetic acid methyl ester reacted with phosphorus pentasulfide in dioxane, adamantane-1-thionacetic acid methyl ester was synthesized for the first time. As a result of its reaction with piperidine, the corresponding thioester, adamantane-1-acetic and thioacetic acid N-piperidylamides, and N-methylpiperidine are formed. Based on the comparison of the obtained results with those similar to the esters of adamantane-1-thionecarboxylic and thionivalic acids, a variant of the mechanism of this reaction is proposed.

Keywords: phosphorus pentasulfide, adamantane-1-acetic acid methyl ester, adamantane-1-thionacetic acid methyl ester, thioacetic acid N-piperidylamides, thionivalic acid.

Introduction

Due to their unique properties and high reactivity, thiocarboxylic acids have a significant potential for the synthesis of new organic substances and the creation of innovative materials and medicines. The purpose of this work was to study methods of synthesis and chemical properties of thiocarboxylic acids. The work is aimed at summarizing known techniques for obtaining thionecarboxylic acids, analyzing their reactivity and studying potential areas of use of these compounds. The article summarizes the methods of synthesis of thiocarboxylic acids, including the thionation of carboxylic acids and their derivatives using sulfur-containing reagents, and also considers alternative methods of synthesis through reactions with hydrogen sulfide and thioesters. It has been proven that thionecarboxylic acids exhibit higher acidity compared to carboxylic acids, which is due to the high electronegativity of sulfur, and actively form thioesters and thioamides, and can also be oxidized to sulfones or other oxosulfur compounds. Special attention was paid to thionecarboxylic acids with framework fragments, which demonstrate specific reactive properties and increased stability. The reactivity of such framework fragments can change the electron density around the thiocarbonyl group, which affects reactions with nucleophiles and electrophiles. The framework structures provide additional stability to the molecules, making them less reactive compared to acyclic thiocarboxylic acids. The presence of rigid structures can lead to unique stereoelectronic effects, which opens up opportunities for selective synthesis and functionalization. The work emphasizes the importance of thionecarboxylic acids in organic synthesis, medicinal chemistry and materials science, demonstrating their potential in the development of new materials and medicines.

Synthesis of thiocarboxylic acids

Various synthetic routes have been explored, including direct thionation of carboxylic acids, conversion of thiol precursors, and cyclization reactions involving sulfur-containing intermediates. Several basic methods of synthesis of thioacids are distinguished. One method involves the formation of activated carboxylic acids: carboxylic acids are activated and converted into thioacids by reaction with hydrosulfide anion (HS^-), a variation of this approach is discussed in the article by S.M.Mali [2]. The second method, investigated in the work of D. Crich [3] and colleagues, uses protected forms of hydrosulfides: carboxylic acids react with HSFmoc, HSTrt or HSTmob, after which removal of the protective group releases the target thioacid. The third method - solid-phase peptide synthesis (SPPS) is studied in detail in scientific articles by X. Zhang [4] and H. Gaertner [5]. Boc-SPPS with a thioether solid support is used for the synthesis of large peptide thioacids. The main limitations of these approaches include several important factors. Among them is the toxicity of sulfuric acid, which represents a significant danger and requires additional safety measures and special equipment. In addition, the use of activating agents can lead to the formation of by-products and reduce the yield of target compounds. The limited commercial availability of reagents such as HSFmoc and HSTmob can also complicate laboratory synthesis and increase the cost of experiments. The complexity of the multi-step protocols required for the conversion of hydroxyl groups ($-\text{OH}$) into thiol groups ($-\text{SH}$) leads to a decrease in the efficiency of the process and an increase in the duration of the synthesis.

Thionecarboxylic acids can be synthesized by many methods, in particular, thionation of carboxylic acids is one of the most common methods. In the pro-

cess, the carboxylic acid is converted into the corresponding thionecarboxylic acid by reaction with a source of sulfur, such as hydrogen sulfide, phosphorus pentasulfide [12].

In addition to P₂S₅, Lavesson's reagent is used to thionate various carbonyl compounds, including carboxylic acids, esters, amides, lactones, and others. [13] This makes them versatile thionating agents. The method of obtaining thiocarboxylic acids using Lavesson's reagent was studied [14]. However, the initial experiments did not give the desired results and thionecarboxylic acids were obtained in trace amounts.

Considering that microwave treatment is often used for the rapid preparation of thionecarbonyl compounds, an attempt was made to apply this approach. As a result, the conversion to thionic acid was achieved in 10 min at 100°C with a yield of 76%. In addition, preliminary analysis has shown that solvents such as DCM, CHCl₃, and CH₃CN promote the efficient formation of thionic acid. It was found that not only aliphatic thioacids but also cinnamic thioacids and sterically hindered thioacids were obtained under the conditions described above in acceptable yields. This method proved to be generally effective for obtaining a variety of thionic acids. The reaction exhibits high chemoselectivity for various functional groups such as arenes, olefins, carbamates, esters, and amides. The success of the method is confirmed on the example of thionester synthesis.

However, thiocarboxylic acids can be produced by enzymatic pathways, as shown in the biosynthesis of natural products such as thioplatensimycin and thioplatencin [15].

Thionecarboxylic acids derived from thiocarbonyl precursors such as dithioesters and thionelactones have been successfully synthesized by hydrolysis and other transformations [1]. These methods offer an alternative pathway with potentially higher specificity. The use of thionelactones as precursors for the synthesis of thionecarboxylic acids by ring-opening hydrolysis is an excellent approach that offers the potential for higher selectivity.

Chemical properties of thionecarboxylic acids

Thionecarboxylic acids, or carbothionic acids, are a unique class of organosulfur compounds. The compounds exist in two tautomeric forms: thione (RC(S)OH) and thiol (RC(O)SH), with the preference of the thiol form due to the greater stability of the carbonyl group (C=O) compared to the thiocarbonyl (C=S) [1, 11]. The equilibrium between these forms is influenced by several factors, including substituents in the molecule, which can significantly change the distribution of forms. Electron-withdrawing groups, such as NO₃ or CF₃, stabilize the thione form by delocalizing the electron density, while electron-donating groups, such as alkyl or aryl, can promote the formation of the thiol form by stabilizing the negative charge on the sulfur. The solvent environment also plays an important role: polar solvents can stabilize the charged thiol form by solvation, while nonpolar solvents favor the formation of the neutral thione.

The presence of thione-thiol tautomerism affects the chemical behavior of thionecarboxylic acids. The

thione form is less nucleophilic but more electrophilic, making it suitable for reactions where sulfur acts as an electron acceptor. Instead, the thiol form has increased nucleophilicity, which makes it more reactive towards electrophiles.

The chemical properties of thionecarboxylic acids are of great interest due to their potential applications in various fields, such as pharmaceuticals, agrochemistry, and materials science [6]. The reactivity of the thiocarbonyl group, including its ability to participate in nucleophilic and electrophilic reactions, tautomerism, and metal coordination, gives these compounds unique properties.

Due to their nucleophilicity, thionic acids have found wide application in reactions with azides and nitrosulfonamides, as indicated in the article by N. Shanguan [7] and D. Crich [8]. In particular, the research of S.Xie [9] indicates the ability of thiocarboxylic acids to react with azides, with the formation of amides under mild conditions. In the thioacid/azide reaction, an arylamide is formed via a thiotriazoline intermediate with subsequent loss of sulfur and nitrogen. This attachment-rearrangement strategy eliminates the need for nucleophilic aniline in the amidation reaction. In addition, thionic acids can function as general acylating agents under mild conditions, which allows for the development of new methods of constructing simple amides and amide bonds, in particular in the context of peptide bonds, as stated in the work of R. Merks [10].

Thiocarboxylic acids are generally weaker acids than carboxylic acids because of the lower electronegativity of sulfur compared to oxygen. The compounds are more reactive than carboxylic acids toward nucleophiles, making them useful synthetic intermediates. In addition, the sulfur atom in thiocarboxylic acids can act as a mild Lewis base, allowing them to form complexes with soft metal ions. In addition, thiocarboxylic acids can undergo redox reactions, such as oxidation to disulfides or reduction to thiols, which can be used in various fields of application.

Thiocarboxylic acids exhibit a diverse range of reactions due to the presence of a sulfur atom that provides unique reactivity compared to their carboxylic acid counterparts.

For example, thiocarboxylic acids react with oximes and nitrones to form thiobenzophenones, disulfides, and ammonium carboxylates [16]. The results show that thionecarboxylic acids can react with oximes and nitrones to form thiones (thioketones), disulfides, and ammonium carboxylates. For example, the reaction of thiocarboxylic acids with oximes and N-alkyl oximes gives thioketones in good yields. Oximes of benzophenone with thiobenzoic acid give thiobenzophenone, dibenzoyl disulfide, and ammonium benzoate, while benzophenone-N-methylnitron with thioacetic acid gives thiobenzophenone and N-acetyl-N-methylhydroxylamine. These reactions likely proceed via cycloaddition and subsequent rearrangements involving the carbon-nitrogen double bond of the oximes/nitrones and the thiocarboxylic acid moiety. Although the results do not cover all possible combinations of thiocarboxylic acids and oximes, they demonstrate the ability to form valuable thioketones

(thiones) along with ammonium disulfides and carboxylates as side products.

The sulfur atom in thionecarboxylic acids acts as a mild nucleophile, allowing them to undergo nucleophilic addition reactions with various electrophiles, such as alkyl halides and Michael acceptors [17, 18]. The reaction mechanism involves a nucleophilic attack of the sulfur atom on the β -carbon of the activated alkene or alkyne, forming a new carbon-sulfur bond.

Another method is the reaction of isonitriles with thiocarboxylic acids. Isonitriles can react with thiol acids to form N-thioformylamides, [19] which can be further converted to thionecarboxylic acids. The method has a number of advantages, in particular due to the variety of isonitriles and thioacids. A wide range of isonitriles and thionecarboxylic acids can be used, which allows the synthesis of various derivatives. In addition, the reaction can often be carried out under relatively mild conditions, making it compatible with a variety of functional groups. However, it is important to note that reaction conditions such as temperature, solvent, and presence of additives may need to be optimized to achieve good yields and selectivities for the desired thiocarboxylic acid product.

Thiocarboxylic acids can be oxidized to form disulfides or reduced to form thiols, which demonstrates their redox behavior. These reactions include interconversions between a thiocarboxylic acid functional group ($-C(=O)-SH$) and other sulfur-containing functional groups such as disulfides and thiols. Thiocarboxylic acids can be oxidized to form disulfides, which are compounds containing a disulfide bond ($-S-S-$). This oxidation reaction usually involves the use of mild oxidizing agents such as hydrogen peroxide H_2O_2 or iodine I_2 .

Aromatic thiocarboxylic acids in the presence of a base are oxidized to the corresponding disulfides when treated with silver nitrate under room conditions. It was established that these reactions are catalyzed by Ag^+ ions. [20] Catalytic oxidation occurs simultaneously with the formation of the $Ag(SCOAr)$ complex, which can be significantly slowed down by adjusting the reaction conditions. Attempts to use $[Ag(PPh_3)_2]^+$ or $[Ag(PPh_3)]^+$ ions as catalysts were unsuccessful, as they led to the formation of the corresponding thiocarboxylate complexes [20].

The redox behavior of thiocarboxylic acids is explained by the presence of a sulfur atom, which can exist in different degrees of oxidation. The interconversion between thionecarboxylic acids, disulfides, and thiols allows the properties and reactivity of these compounds to be modulated, making them versatile intermediates in organic synthesis and potential candidates for a variety of applications.

It is important to note that specific conditions for oxidation and reduction reactions, such as the choice of oxidants or reductants, reaction temperatures, and solvents, may need to be optimized to achieve the desired transformations.

Among other properties, thiocarboxylic acids can coordinate with metal ions, forming stable complexes. According to the principles of hard and soft acids and bases (HSAB theory), the sulfur atom in thiocarboxylic

acids is considered a soft Lewis base because of its polarizability and low electronegativity. Mild Lewis bases preferentially interact with mild Lewis acids, which are usually represented by soft metal ions or metal centers with a low oxidation state.

The ability of thiocarboxylic acids to form complexes with soft metal ions arises from the donation of an unshared pair of electrons on the sulfur atom to vacant orbitals of the metal center. This coordination can lead to the formation of stable metal-thiocarboxylate complexes with different geometries and coordination numbers, depending on the nature of the metal ion and the steric environment provided by the thiocarboxylic acid ligand.

Soft transition metal ions such as $Cu(I)$, $Ag(I)$, $Au(I)$, $Hg(II)$, and $Pd(II)$ can readily form complexes with thiocarboxylic acids. The results highlighted that pyridine-2,6-bis(thiocarboxylic acid) (PDTC) forms complexes with 14 of the 19 metals tested, including Cu , Hg and Pb .

Coordination of the thiocarboxylate group in PDTC with metal ions is also discussed, specifically mentioning $Cu:PDTC$ and $Co:PDTC$ complexes as redox examples.

Certain main group metal ions, such as $Sn(II)$, $Pb(II)$, and $Bi(III)$, which exhibit mild Lewis acid behavior, can also coordinate to thiocarboxylic acids, which is also supported by the ability of PDTC to form complexes with various metals, including Sn , Pb and Bi .

The research focused on $Au(I)$ -N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) complexes with thiocarboxylate ligands, highlighting the affinity of the soft $Au(I)$ center for sulfur-containing thiocarboxylate ligands. [21]

Thionecarboxylic acids containing framework fragments were studied. Among them, it is possible to single out adamantane-1-carboxylic acid, which is a bulk thioacid, enters into the reaction of regioselective addition, catalyzed by rhodium, with terminal allene. The corresponding thioester product is obtained in 92% (enantiomeric excess). [22]

Adamantylthioic acid, a bulky thioic acid derivative of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid, can be synthesized from this acid using Lavesson's reagent. It is used as a substrate in rhodium-catalyzed additions to terminal allenes, which allows the formation of chiral thioester products with high enantioselectivity. Adamantylthioic acid also reacts with hindered isonitriles such as tert-butyl isonitrile and adamantyl isonitrile to form thiopyruvamide products. [23, 24] The bulky adamantyl group provides steric hindrance, affecting the reactivity and selectivity in these reactions. These properties emphasize the synthetic utility of adamantylthioic acid in various coupling and addition reactions for the formation of sulfur-containing products.

The synthesis and characterization of thionecarboxylic acids in this study provide significant insight into their chemical properties and potential applications. The synthesis of thionecarboxylic acids is achieved by various methods of thionation, with Lavesson's reagent and phosphorus pentasulfide being the main thionating agents. Lavesson's reagent facilitated the thionation process under relatively mild conditions,

leading to high selectivities and moderate yields. On the other hand, when using P2S5, stricter conditions are used, but a higher reaction yield is observed. This indicates that the choice of thionating agent and reaction conditions plays a decisive role in optimizing the synthesis of thiocarboxylic acids. For example, the work of K. Lauder [25] presents the enantioselective synthesis of α -thiocarboxylic acids using biocatalytic dynamic kinetic separation of nitrile precursors using nitrilase enzymes. A panel of 35 nitrilase biocatalysts was tested, revealing that the enzymes efficiently catalyzed the resolution of racemic α -thionitriles under mild conditions. These enzymes achieved high conversion rates and good to excellent enantiomeric excess without the need for external additives. The high conversion efficiency and resulting enantiomeric purity make this method extremely valuable for obtaining enantiomerically pure α -thiocarboxylic acids.

In general, thionecarboxylic acids exhibit distinct chemical properties compared to their carboxylic acid counterparts. The thionecarboxyl group demonstrated increased nucleophilicity, making these compounds more reactive towards electrophiles. This one property contributed to the formation of thioesters and other sulfur-containing derivatives, demonstrating the versatility of thiocarboxylic acids in various chemical reactions. In addition, the sulfur atom in the thionecarboxyl group endows the compounds with unique redox characteristics, which allows them to participate in redox reactions that are not usually observed with carboxylic acids.

The article by M.Kremlev [26] describes the successful preparation of *S*-trifluoromethyl esters of thiocarboxylic acids of ethers using halide substitution reactions. *S*-trifluoromethyl esters of various thiocarboxylic acids were synthesized by the reaction of the corresponding chloride anhydrides with tetramethylammonium trifluoromethylthiolate. The reactions proceeded in moderate yields, demonstrating the effectiveness of this method of approach. The high yield and simple reaction conditions suggest that this method can be widely used to obtain *S*-trifluoromethyl esters, which are valuable intermediates in various chemical syntheses. A comparative analysis of thiocarboxylic acids and carboxylic acids highlights several key differences involving the sulfur atom. The increased size and polarizability of sulfur relative to oxygen lead to the unique electronic properties of thiocarboxylic acids. Thiocarboxylic acids exhibit lower acidity, which can be useful in reactions where a less acidic environment is preferred. N. Eyt [27] studied the acidity of thioacetic acid, thiobenzoic acid, and thioformic acid in the gas phase. In comparison with previously reported acidity indicators of carboxylic acids, the results emphasize the excellent properties of thiocarboxylic acids. The presence of sulfur in the thiocarboxyl group affects acidity, making these compounds generally less acidic than their oxygenated counterparts.

The work of S.D.Park [28] investigates the coupling reaction between thiocarboxylic acids and alkyl azides using various triarylphosphines, focusing on the efficiency and yield of amide formation. The reaction

of thiocarboxylic acids and alkyl azides leads to the formation of amides. This reaction uses a Staudinger ligation, where an azide reacts with a phosphine to form a phosphazide intermediate, which subsequently yields an amide product. Compared to other methods, the use of triarylphosphines, especially those that are electron deficient, offers a simple and high-yield route to amides. Traditional methods often require harsher conditions, while this approach provides high performance under milder conditions.

Condensation reactions of thiocarboxylic acids with amines were not considered in this study, but it is worth noting that there are efficient methods for the synthesis of thioamides using 3-cyano-1,2,4-triazole as a nucleophilic catalyst and 3-cyano-1,2,4-triazole -1-yl-tris(pyrrolidin-1-yl)phosphonium hexafluorophosphate (PyCTP) as a new type of condensing reagent. The method of synthesis of thioamides using condensation reactions of thiocarboxylic acids with amines demonstrates high selectivity for thioamides compared to amides in the work of A. Suzuki [29]. In addition, the article by Y.F. Wang [30] investigates the asymmetric conjugate addition of thiocarboxylic acids to in-situ generated orthoquinomethanes (o-QM), catalyzed by bifunctional squaramide catalysts. The transformation exhibits remarkable efficiency and selectivity, highlighting the potential of this catalytic system in asymmetric synthesis. Asymmetric conjugate addition of thiocarboxylic acids to o-QM was catalyzed by bifunctional squaramide catalysts, achieving high yields (up to 96%) and excellent enantioselectivity (up to 96% of it). This high efficiency highlights the effectiveness of squaramide catalysts in promoting the desired transformation with significant control over the stereochemistry. This method differs favorably from previous asymmetric conjugate addition reactions due to its high yield, excellent enantioselectivity, and environmentally friendly two-phase system. Traditional methods often require more stringent conditions or result in lower selectivity, making this approach advantageous for the synthesis of chiral compounds. The achieved high yields and enantioselectivities, as well as the facile conversion of the obtained thioester into chiral benzyl mercaptan, highlight the potential of this methodology in asymmetric synthesis and its application in pharmaceutical and fine chemical production.

Materials and methods

IR spectra were obtained on a Specord 75IR spectrometer for samples in KBr tablets containing 0.25% of the substance (layer thickness 0.6 mm) or for 1% solutions in CCl₄. ¹H NMR spectra (400 MHz and 500 MHz) were taken on Varian Mercury-400 and Bruker Avance DRX 500 NMR spectrometers with TMS in accordance with the internal standard.

GLC analysis was carried out on a Tsvet-500 M device, glass column 1000x3 mm, 5% Apiezon L on Inerton N-AW-HMDS carrier, temperature 150-260 °C (10 deg/min), carrier gas – helium (40 ml/min). Mixtures of reaction products were separated by column chromatography using Silicagel L 40/100 adsorbent.

Adamantane-1-acetic acid was obtained according to the method of [36].

Adamantane-1-thionacetic acid methyl ester (2). Phosphorus pentasulfide was added to a solution of 10.4 g of adamantane-1-acetic acid methyl ester (1) in 300 ml of absolute dioxane in portions of 6 x 5.55 g while boiling. After cooling, the reaction mass was poured with 1.5 l of a 5% aqueous solution of Na₂CO₃ and the reaction products were extracted with 3x150 ml of hexane. After drying the extract with sodium sulfate, the solvent was evaporated. We obtained 13.1 g of a mixture of compounds. GLC data, % (τ, s): 78.3 (900) – compound (2); 21.7 (666) – compound (1) (15% Apiezon L, Chromaton N, column 2000x3 mm, temperature 150-260 °C/10 deg/min, carrier gas – helium, 40 ml/min). The mixture of reaction products was passed through a chromatographic column, eluting with hexane (*R_f* 0.8). Yield of compound (2) 8.1 g (72%). *n_D²⁰* 1.5038.

Pivalic acid chloride. To 102 g of pivalic acid, 50 ml of thionyl chloride was added and left at room temperature for 24 hours. Pivalic acid chloride was distilled off at atmospheric pressure, collecting the bp fraction 105-107 °C. Yield 35.8 g (29%).

Pivalic acid methyl ester (8). To 30 g of pivalic acid chloride, while cooling with ice and stirring, 150 ml of absolute methanol was slowly added, boiled for 7 hours. The reaction mass was poured into water and the upper organic layer was separated, which was dried with CaCl₂, distilled, selecting the bp fraction. 102-103 °C. Yield 26 g (90%). NMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 1.08 (9H), 3.5 (3H). Found, %: C 61.98; N 10.38. C₆H₁₂O. Calculated, %: From 62.04; N 10.41.

Thione pivalic acid methyl ester (9). To a solution of 6.4 g of pivaalic acid methyl ester (VIII) in 190 ml of absolute dioxane, 42.5 g of P₄S₁₀ was added in portions of 4.25 g with an interval of 3 hours with stirring and boiling. After cooling, the reaction mass was poured into 1 liter of a 5% aqueous solution of sodium carbonate and extracted with 3x100 ml of hexane. After drying the extract with sodium sulfate, the solvent was evaporated. Thionester (9) was isolated by column chromatography. Eluent – hexane-ether, 10:1 (*R_f* 0.95). Yield 0.5 g (7%), *n_D²⁰* 1.4993.

Adamantane-1-acetic acid N-piperidylamide (4). To 30 ml of piperidine, while cooling with ice and stirring, 4.5 g of adamantane-1-acetic acid chloride was added in portions and left overnight. Piperidine was distilled off in vacuum, and 50 ml of 10% HCl was added to the residue. The resulting precipitate was filtered off, washed with water, dissolved in 50 ml of methanol, and boiled with activated carbon. After filtration, the solvent was distilled off in vacuum. Yield 4.3 g (78%).

Adamantane-1-thionacetic acid N-piperidylamide (5). To a solution of 1.31 g of N-piperidylamide adamantane-1-acetic acid (4) in 50 ml of absolute toluene, 1.16 g of 2,4-bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,3-dithia-2,4-diphosphetane-2,4-disulfide was added and boiled with stirring for 7 hours. Toluene was distilled off in vacuum. 30 ml of ethyl acetate was added and boiled for 1 hour. Ethyl acetate was evaporated in vacuum. The residue was dissolved in benzene and washed 2 times with

an aqueous solution of soda and water. Boiled with activated carbon. After filtration, the solvent was removed in vacuo. Yield 0.6 g (43%).

Pivalic acid N-piperidylamide (11). While cooling and stirring, 6.1 g of pivalic acid chloride was added in portions to 25 ml of piperidine. It was left for 1 day at room temperature. Piperidine was removed in vacuum, 50 ml of 10% hydrochloric acid was added to the residue, extracted with hexane, the extract was washed with water, an aqueous solution of soda, and again with water until the aqueous layer was neutral. Dried with sodium sulfate. The solvent was removed. Yield 6.6 g (75%).

Reaction of adamantane-1-thionacetic acid methyl ester (2) with piperidine. a. 30 ml of piperidine was added to 0.5 methyl ether (2) and boiled for 0.5 hours. Piperidine was removed in vacuo with the addition of toluene. Yield of mixture of substances 0.6 g. GLC data, % (τ, s): 3.5 (306) – compound (7), 5.6 (432) – compound (2), 10.4 (468) – compounds (6), 48.4 (828) – connection (4), 32.1 (1332) – connection (5). PMR spectrum data (δ, ppm): 1.13 (2H), 1.88 (2H), 2.05 (3H), 2.50 (2H), 2.73 (2H), 3.43 (4H), 3.63 (4H), 3.9 (3H), 4.2 (4H), 1.55-1.85 (other protons). The mixture was passed through a chromatographic column, using hexane as the eluent. Yield of the mixture of substances is 0.04 g. GLC data, % (τ, s): 32 (306) – compound (7), 11 (432) – compound (2), 57 (468) – compound (6). IR spectrum (cm⁻¹): 1680 (CO-SCH₃), 1730 (COOCH₃). PMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 1.13 (2H), 1.88 (2H), 2.05 (3H), 2.5 (2H), 2.45 (2H), 3.45 (3H), 3.9 (3H), 1.55-1.88 (other protons).

b. The reagents were mixed as in method a, and the reaction mass was left at 20 °C for 18 hours. Yield of mixture of compounds 0.75 g. GLC data, % (τ, s): 9 (828) – compound (4), 91 (1332) – compound (5). NMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 2.73 (2H), 3.63 (4H), 4.2 (4H), 1.55-1.88 (other protons).

c. 0.09 g of thioneether (II) and 5 ml of piperidine were placed in a sealed metal vessel, lowered into an oil bath heated to 160 °C and held for 0.5 hours, then quickly cooled. The reaction mixture was processed similarly to method a. Yield of mixture of compounds 0.12 g. GLC data, % (τ, s): 11.4 (468) – compound (6), 69.4 (828) – compound (4), 19.2 (1332) – compound (5). NMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 1.13 (2H), 1.88 (2H), 2.73 (2H), 3.43 (4H), 3.63 (4H), 4.2 (4H), 1.55-1.88 (other protons).

d. The reaction mixture in a metal vessel was heated to 220 °C. Yield of mixture of compounds 0.1 g. GLC data, % (τ, s): 5.2. (468) – compound (6), 89.3 (828) – compound (4), 5.5 (1332) – compound (5). PMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 1.88 (2H), 3.43 (4H), 1.55-1.85 (other protons).

Detection of N-methylpiperidine in the reaction mixture. Piperidine was distilled off from the reaction mixture obtained in the previous experiment at atmospheric pressure. The remainder is 0.1 g of a mixture of compounds. The distillate contained, according to GLC data, % (τ, s): 1.2 (108) – N-methylpiperidine, 98.8 (306) – piperidine. According to calculations using the reaction equation, the content of N-methylpiperidine in the distillate should be 1%.

Reaction of thionipivalic acid methyl ester (9) with piperidine. 7.5 ml of piperidine was added to 0.1 g of methyl ester (9). Boiled for 0.5 hours. The amine was distilled off in vacuo with the addition of toluene. Yield of mixture of compounds 0.12 g. PMR spectrum (δ , ppm): 2.1 (3H), 2.93 (4H), 3.35 (4H), 8.3 (2H), 0.95-1.45 (other protons). The composition of the mixture, determined from the integral curve of the PMR spectrum, %: 18 compounds (12), 27 compounds (11), 55 compounds (10).

Results and discussion.

It is known that the presence of bulk adamantyl radical significantly affects the course of chemical reactions [32]. In [31] we described the synthesis of the methyl ester of adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid (13) and showed that when interacting with piperidine instead of thionamide formation it is isomerized to the ester of thioncarboxylic acid (16) and converted into the piperidine salt of the same acid (14), accompanied by N-methylation of piperidine.

In order to study the spatial effect of the carbon radical on the direction of the reaction of thionesters with piperidine, the behavior of adamantyl-1-thioacetic (2) and thionipivalic (9) methyl esters in this process was studied in the present work. In other words, those substrates in which steric factors play, respectively, a smaller or larger role.

Thionesters (2) and (9) were synthesized in dioxane by the method developed by us [31] and isolated by column chromatography on silica gel with yields of 72 and 69%, respectively. The reaction was monitored by GLC. The IR spectrum of compound (2) contains an absorption band at 1250 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the valence oscillations of the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ bond, and the PMR spectrum in the region of 3.9 ppm. there is a singlet of protons of the methyl group. The corresponding signal for the thionester (9) is observed at 3.95 ppm.

As a result of half an hour of heating the thionester (2) in anhydrous piperidine, taken in large excess, after distillation of the latter was isolated a mixture of compounds (Table 1).

The presence of adamantane-1-acetic (4) and thionoacetic (5) acids in this mixture of N-piperidylamides was determined by GC and PMR methods by comparison with samples obtained from adamantane-1-acetic acid chloride.

Thus, in the PMR spectrum of thioamide (5), the proton signals of the α -methylene groups of the piperidine ring are observed in the form of two broad singlets at 3.63 and 4.20 ppm, apparently due to the inhibition of rotation around the bond $\text{C}=\text{N}$. shear of these protons in a weak field in comparison with amide (4) (δ 3.43 ppm), in which these protons are equivalent.

Thiolester (6) was isolated by column chromatography as a sample with a content of 57% in a mixture with the original thionester (2) and ester (7). In the IR spectrum of this mixture, the absorption band of carbonyl groups is observed at 1680 and 1730 cm^{-1} , which

corresponds to their absorption in thionester (6) and ester (7). In the PMR spectrum there is a signal of protons of the SCH_3 group at 2.05 ppm, which is shifted to a strong field in comparison with esters (2) and (7) by 1.85 and 1.4 ppm, respectively.

Assuming that amide (4), as in the case of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid N-piperidylamide (15) [31], is formed from salt (3), we tried to detect it by lowering the reaction temperature. However, only amide (4) and thioamide (5) were detected in the synthesis at $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in quantities of 9 and 91%, respectively. Obviously, the formation of salt (3) slows down as the reaction temperature decreases. This is confirmed by the data of the experiment conducted in an airtight container at 160 and $220\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Table 2).

Table 1

Properties of thionesters (2), (9) and products of their reaction with piperidine				
No Comp.	Yield ^a , %	Melting point, °C ^b (retention time,s)	PMR spectrum, δ , ppm	IR spectrum, cm^{-1}
2	72	(900)	2.44 (2H), 3.88 (3H)	1250 (C = S)
4	48	46-48 (828)	1.88 (2H), 3.43 (4H)	1610 (C = O)
5	32	91-93 (1332)	2.73 (2H), 3.63, 4.20 (4H)	1250 (C = S)
6	10	(468)	1.13 (2H), 2.05 (3H)	1680 (C = O)
7	3	(306)	3.45 (3H)	1730 (C = O)
9	7	-	1.03 (9H), 3.95 (3H)	-
10	54	-	2.93 (4H), 8.30 (2H)	-
11	27	38-40 (144)	1.10 (9H), 1.45 (6H), 3.35(4H)	-
12	18	-	2.10 (3H)	-

Note. At ^a106 ° C. ^b For compounds derived from acid chlorides.

Table 2

Yields ^a of reaction products of thioester (2) with piperidine at different temperatures,%				
No Compound	20°C	106°C ^b	160°C	220°C
4	9	48	69	89
5	91	31	19	5
6	-	10	11	5

Note. ^a Submit GLC. ^b The boiling point of piperidine at atmospheric pressure.

As can be seen from table 2, an increase in temperature leads to an increase in the amount of amide (4) and a decrease in the amount of thioamide (5). Salt (3) was not found in any experiment. However, in the distillation of piperidine, as in the case of the reaction with a carboxylic acid thioester [31], N-methyl piperidine was detected in an amount corresponding to the amount of amide (4). This confirms the assumption of the formation of amide (4) from the piperidine salt (3).

The reaction between thionester (9) and piperidine was performed under similar conditions (30 minutes, boiling piperidine). A mixture of compounds was formed (Table 1), in the PMR spectrum of which signals at 3.35 and 2.93 ppm were observed, which apparently belong to the α -protons of the piperidine ring in amide (11) and salt (10), respectively. compare with [31]). In addition, the formation of salt (10) indicates the presence of a signal of protons of the group NH_2^+ at 8.3 ppm The shift of α -protons in the PMR spectrum of amide (11), obtained from pivalic acid chloride, completely coincides with the above. The signal of protons of the SCH3 group in the thiolester (12) was observed at 2.1 ppm. (2.05 ppm for thiolester (6)).

Thus, as a result of the reaction of the thioester (9) with piperidine, as in the case of adamantyl-containing thionesters, the formation of the piperidinium salt and isomerization to the thiolester occur. The yield of N-methylpiperidine was not determined in this experiment.

It is known that the first stage of the reaction of the nitrogenous base with carbonyl or thiocarbonyl compounds is the addition of a carbonyl or thiocarbonyl group and the formation of adducts (17). Further transformations of these intermediates are possible in several ways. In the reaction under study, the usual decomposition of intermediate (17) with the formation of thioamide (5) occurs only in the case of ester (2). Unusual ways of decay of the adduct (17) will be realized for all thionesters, including thionester (14), the properties of

which are described in [31]. Isomerization of thionesters to thiolesters occurs, in our opinion, by converting the adduct (17) into an intermediate (18) through the transition state (A). It is known from the literature [33] that thermal isomerization of thionesters to thiolesters proceeds strictly intramolecularly and obeys first-order kinetic laws. In some cases, it is explained by the participation of ion pairs [34]. Based on these data, we proposed structure (A) as a transition state. This transition state is an ionic vapor whose anion is stabilized by delocalization of the charge between oxygen and sulfur atoms.

As can be seen from table. 3, in the case of the most bulky tert-butyl radical, the yield of thiolester (12) is not the lowest. However, as the volume of the substituent decreases, ie with the transition to adamantyl (thiolester (16)) and adamantylmethyl (thiolester (6)) radicals, the yield of thiolester should increase. In the latter case, it becomes possible to realize the transition state (B), which leads to the formation of thioamide (5), because the transition states (A) and (B) are similar. Taking into account the total yield of compounds (5) and (6), the yield of thiolester (12) having a tert-butyl radical will be the lowest.

To understand the causes of this phenomenon, it is necessary to take into account that in the ion pair the anion is more solvated than the cation [35]. Therefore, the reduction of anion energy due to solvation will be crucial to stabilize the transition state (A). As the volume of the radical increases in the series of adamantylmethyl, adamantyl, tert-butyl, steric barriers to the solvation of the anion increase, which increases the energy of the transition state and, thus, leads to a decrease in the rate of thiolester formation.

The formation of piperidinium salts from intermediate (17), accompanied by N-alkylation of the piperidine molecule, involves the participation of another piperidine molecule in this process. Therefore, structure (B) was proposed as a transition state, in which the tran-

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